

DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF A DOUBLE-SIDED INCLINED MIXED-MODE SOLAR DRYER FOR SUSTAINABLE POST-HARVEST PROCESSING

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Abstract

The development and performance evaluation of a double-sided inclined mixed-mode solar dryer for sustainable post-harvest drying in developing regions are presented in this work. Constructed using locally available materials, it consists of two solar collectors, a drying chamber, and a solar store. The dryer was designed for a maximum load of 60 kg and integrates indirect solar drying modes with two collectors to optimize solar capture. It was tested in Akure, Nigeria (Latitude 7.25°N, Longitude 5.08°E). Thermal performance and drying efficiency were evaluated under both no-load and load conditions using yam, fish, pepper, and okra. The measured parameters were temperatures and weights. The products were weighed before and after drying each day to determine the moisture loss. Results showed an average drying chamber temperatures ranging between 35 and 60°C, at 28°C ambient temperature. It has achieved an overall average exergetic efficiency of 46.35% with a collector efficiency of 69.09%. Nutritional analysis indicated enhanced nutrient preservation over open sun drying having protein content of 5.96%. This innovation supports SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) through passive, low-cost, efficient energy use for food preservation.

Keywords
solar dryer
nutritional analysis
mixed-mode
double-sided
collectors

1. INTRODUCTION

Post-harvest food loss remains a critical issue across sub-Saharan Africa, where millions of tons of agricultural produce are lost annually due to inefficient preservation and drying methods. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), up to 40% of food is lost between harvest and consumption, primarily due to inadequate processing and preservation technologies [1]. Among various preservation methods, drying remains one of the oldest and most practical approaches for extending the shelf life of perishable agricultural products [2]. Traditionally, this has been done through open sun drying which involves placing produce directly under the sun on mats, rooftops, or bare ground.

While open sun drying is low-cost and accessible, it presents critical drawbacks. These include vulnerability to dust, pests, microbial infestation, nutrient degradation, and reliance on unpredictable weather conditions and long drying times. In addition, the method is labour-intensive, time-consuming, and often results in poor product quality due to uneven or incomplete drying. [3–4]. These limitations not only compromise food safety and quality but also result in significant economic losses for smallholder farmers and rural communities. Furthermore, they underscore the urgent need for improved drying systems that balance efficiency, affordability, and sustainability.

The global shift toward climate-resilient agricultural practices has brought solar drying technologies into sharper focus. Solar dryers offer a cleaner, more efficient, and environmentally friendly solution by harnessing abundant solar radiation to drive the drying process [5]. Innovations in dryer configuration such as mixed-mode systems that integrate both direct and indirect solar heating enhance thermal performance while protecting food from external contaminants [6]. Such technologies directly contribute to achieving the United Nations Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 2 (Zero Hunger), Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), and Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production).

Traditionally, drying is carried out in an open field, and is the most widespread method used in developing countries, because it is the simplest and cheapest method of preserving foodstuffs. The traditional methods of drying pepper are by open sun-drying and smoking which involves simply laying the product in the direct sunlight. Traditional drying has some disadvantages which includes exposure to adverse weather conditions like rain, dust, wind, as well as infestation insects. Also, possibility of product damage can occur due to rodents, birds or any other animal infestation of the products. This ultimately slows down the drying rate, causing mould formation, thereby causing deterioration and decomposition of the product [7–8]. The process also requires large area of land and takes time. In order to protect the products from above mentioned disadvantages and also to accelerate the time for drying the products, control the final moisture and reduce wastage through bacterial action, different types of solar dryers have been adopted [9]. Recently, efforts to improve sun drying led to building solar dryers.

Solar dryers are specialized devices that control the drying process and protect agricultural produce from damage by insect pests, dust and rain. In comparison to natural sun drying, solar dryers generate higher temperatures, lower relative humidity, lower product moisture content and reduce spoilage during the drying process. In addition, it takes up less space, takes more time and relatively inexpensive compared to artificial mechanical dryers. Thus, solar drying is a better alternative solution to all the drawbacks of natural drying and artificial mechanical drying [10–11]. Aderemi *et al.* [12] conducted a study in which the construction materials were locally sourced and drying of maize and gmelina seeds sample were carried out both in the open sun and the solar dryer for five days. The maize seeds sample with initial mass of 300 g lost 75% moisture content to open sun drying and 94% to solar drying. The gmelina seeds sample with initial mass of 400 g at the end of three days drying period lost 45% moisture content in the open sun and 63 % in solar dryer.

Akinola [13] developed mixed-mode solar food dryer for domestic use and its performance evaluated. The dryer combined both direct and indirect type of solar dryers. The dryer was designed for a maximum food load of 60 kg. It was tested on zero-load condition for 5 days. Afterwards food products such as pepper, yam and okro were dried for 15 days. A maximum temperature of 99°C was recorded and the highest drying temperature was 69.1°C. He obtained 66.95% as an average daily thermal efficiency. Analysis showed that the system performed better than direct and indirect dryer with efficiency value of 56.5% and 58%. It also reduced the drying time of pepper by 44%, yam 50%, waterleaf by 75% and okro by 70% against what was obtained in direct sun drying.

Bolaji [14] discussed the advantages of using direct application of solar thermal energy by employing some means of collecting solar radiation with the result that elevated temperature and in turn, lower relative humidity is achieved for drying fish in Nigeria. The use of solar dryer can produce well dried and dust free products. The contact between fish and flies which is virtually impossible to eliminate under traditional technique of fish smoking could be constantly eliminated with the use of solar dryer. Ampratwum and Dorvlo [15] evaluated the performance of solar cabinet dryer under no-load as an air heating-system. The dryer was operated for 28 days, and results showed that the dryer attained an average temperature of 81.3°C. A foldable solar dryer was designed and developed by [16], and evaluated for mango preservation. The work revealed that that a final moisture content of 10% to 12% is acceptable for mangoes stored in a greenhouse solar dryer.

Two passive solar dryers made from locally available materials were designed and developed by Alonge and Adeboye [17] for the drying of some African vegetables. The solar dryers were tested for okra, pepper and other vegetables to evaluate the drying rates of these products. The results show that the drying rate of the direct passive solar dryer was higher than that of the indirect passive solar dryer. Other authors have worked on solar dryers and in all cases reported that using a cabinet is more efficient than direct sun drying [18–23].

This work presents a double-sided inclined mixed-mode solar dryer, designed to improve energy collection and heat transfer through a passive system. The system incorporates two inclined solar collectors on either side of the drying cabinet to increase solar gain throughout the day, regardless of the sun's position. This structural innovation enables consistent temperature distribution within the chamber and enhances drying efficiency. The dryer was fabricated using locally available, cost-effective materials, making it suitable for adoption in rural, off-grid areas.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The materials used in the construction of the solar drying cabinet include: hardwood, plywood, hinges and handle for the dryer's door, nails and glue as fasteners and adhesives, insect net for air inlet and outlet, foam, galvanized metal sheet, silicon sealants, wire mesh trays, galvanized iron rod, thermometers, paints (black and white), and plain glass. The top was made of glass for easy absorption, reflection and radiation of heat but reduces the flow of heat energy out of the systems. The door of the dryer was made of plywood and the opposite side was constructed with hardwood. Being a double mixed solar dryer, solar collectors were designed for both sides.

2.2 Design Calculation

2.2.1 Energy Balance on a Flat Plate Collector

The energy balance on a flat plate collector can be obtained by equating the total heat gained to the total heat lost by the heat absorber as expressed in equation (1) [24].

$$\tau I_T A_c = Q_U + Q_K + Q_C + Q_R + Q_\rho \quad (1)$$

Where:

I_T is the rate of total radiation incident on the absorber's surface (Wm^{-2});

τ is the transmissivity constant

A_c is the collector area (m^2);

Q_U is the rate of useful energy collected by the air (W);

Q_K is the rate of conduction losses from the absorber (W);

Q_C is the rate of convective losses from the absorber (W);

Q_R is the rate of long wave re-radiation from the absorber (W);

Q_ρ is the rate of reflection losses from the absorber (W).

The three heat loss terms Q_K , Q_C and Q_R are usually combined into one-term Q_L is expressed by equation (2).

$$Q_L = Q_K + Q_C + Q_R \quad (2)$$

The reflected energy from the absorber is given by equation (3).

$$Q_R = \tau I_T A_c \rho \quad (3)$$

Where:

Q_L is the combined rate of heat losses (W)

ρ is the reflection coefficient of the absorber.

The useful energy of the system is determined by equations (4) and (5)

$$Q_u = \tau I_T (1 - \rho) A_c - Q_L \quad (4)$$

For an absorber, $(1 - \rho) = \alpha$.

Therefore,

$$Q_U = \alpha \tau I_T A_c - Q_L \quad (5)$$

where:

α is the absorptivity of transparent surface.

2.2.2 Energy Loss

When the flat plate collector is exposed to solar radiation, its temperature rises. As a result, at high intensity more than the ambient temperature there is an infiltration loss of energy to the surrounding. Also, heat energy is lost through the top mainly by convection and radiation, and through the bottom and side panels by conduction.

' Q_L ' composed of different convection and radiation parts, is as presented in equation (6) [25].

$$Q_L = U_L A_c (t_c - t_a), \quad (6)$$

where:

U_L is the overall heat transfer coefficient of the absorber ($W^{-2} m^{-1} K$);

A_c is the collector area (m^2)

t_c is the temperature of the collector's absorber ($^{\circ}C$);

t_a is the ambient air temperature ($^{\circ}C$)

The useful energy gained by the collector is expressed by equation (7).

$$Q_U = (\alpha \tau) I_T A_c - U_L A_c (t_c - t_a) \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the energy per unit area (q_u) of the collector is given by equation (8).

$$q_u = (\alpha \tau) I_T - U_L (t_c - t_a) \quad (8)$$

The thermal efficiency of the collector is determined by equation (9).

$$\eta = \frac{q_u}{I_T} \tag{9}$$

2.3 Solar Load through Transparent Surface

2.3.1 Fenestration Heat Balance: Solar Heat Gain through (Glass)

The heat balance between unit areas of sunlight for a glazing material at its thermal environment at any instant is given by equation (10).

$$AI_t + UA(t_d - t_a) = Q_{Rg} + Q_{Sg} + Q_{\tau g} + Q_{RCO} + Q_{RCI} \tag{10}$$

Where:

A is the area covered (m²)

U is the overall heat transfer coefficient (Wm⁻²k⁻¹)

I_t is the insolation constant (Wm⁻²)

Q_{Rg} is the heat reflected from the glass (W)

Q_{Sg} is the heat stored in the glass (W)

Q_{τg} is the heat transmitted through the glass (W)

Q_{RCO} is the rate of heat flux outward by radiation and convection (W)

Q_{RCI} is the rate of heat flux inward by radiation and convection (W)

The total instantaneous rate of heat gain through glazing is as expressed in equation (11).

$$Q_T = I_p + I_d + Q_{RCO} \tag{11}$$

Where:

Q_T is the total heat admission through glass (W)

I_d is the diffuse radiation

I_p is the direct radiation

The diffuse radiation as direct radiation, (direct radiation is dominant for incident angles below 60°), then, the total heat gain per unit area is given by equation (12).

$$Q_A = I_t \tau + N_i(\alpha I_t) + U(t_a - t_d) \tag{12}$$

Where:

Q_A is the total heat gain per unit area (Wm⁻²)

N_i is the inward flowing fraction of the absorbed radiation

α is the absorptance of glass

αI_t is the radiation absorbed by glass

τ is the transmissivity

2.4 Collector's Inclination: Vertical and Slanting Heights

The collector's inclination (angle of tilt) is 17.25° to the horizontal and has an area of 0.32 m². The vertical height of the collector is obtained from the right-angled triangle ABC as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1: collector inclination

2.5 The Exergetic Efficiency

The exergetic efficiency of the dryer is determined using equations (13), (14) and (15).

The heat Exergy of the dryer, X (W),

$$X = \left(\frac{T - T_a}{T} \right) q \tag{13}$$

Heat Energy, Y (W),

$$Y = \left(\frac{T_a}{T}\right)q \quad (14)$$

Exegetic Efficiency

$$\eta_x = \frac{x}{y} \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

2.6 Experimental Procedure

The dryer was tested during the rainy season using panla also known as Alaska Pollock (*Gadus chalcogrammus*), pepper (*Capsicum annum*), white yam (*Dioscorea alata*), and okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) as specimen during the test. The solar collectors were connected into the cabinet at the angle of inclination. Thermometers were inserted at each cabinet and at both sides of the two solar collectors labelled A and B respectively. The measurements were taken during the day at 60 minutes interval throughout all the experiments.

The following parameters were measured between the 0900 and 1800 hours (local time) each day; the ambient, Solar collectors and dryer's temperature using mercury-in-glass thermometers and the weights of the products using weight balance, and moisture content were estimated using the weight balance.

2.6.1 Testing on No-Load

No-load test was carried out on the dryer; parameters were measured and recorded hourly. It was assumed here that the available energy is equal to the useful energy as no product was dried, and no control experiment was set up.

2.6.2 Testing on Load

The products were weighed each day at the start and close of experiment to determine the moisture content. Thermometers were suspended in both the drying chamber and collector area for easy reading of temperature. Temperatures of ambient and cabinet were taken at interval. Control experiment was set up in the open (direct sun drying) for each of experiment. The products were weighed each day at the start and close of experiment to determine the moisture content. Temperatures were taken and averages were recorded. Thermometers were suspended in both sides of the drying chamber and solar collector for easy reading. Control experiment was set up in the open (direct sun drying) for each of the experiment.

The fabricated dryer is shown in Plate 1, the isometric drawing in Fig. 2, and the orthographic drawing is shown in Fig. 3.

Plate 1: Picture of the double-sided mixed-mode solar dryer

Fig. 2: The Isometric view of the double-sided inclined mixed-mode Solar Food dryer

Fig 2: Orthographic views of the dryer.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Result of no-load test/readings

A no-load test was carried out on the dryer. Temperatures (ambient, cabinet and solar collectors) were measured and recorded at 60 minutes interval as shown in Fig. 4. It was assumed here that the available energy was equal to the useful energy since no product was dried and no control experiment was set up.

Fig 4: Average temperature of unloaded dryer against time

The temperature of the solar store was measured only in the morning and evening and not hourly so as not to add load to it, thereby preventing heat loss. It was taken in the morning after the store had released heat to the chamber at night and in the evening to know the amount of the heat it has trapped. Fig. 4 shows the average daily temperature against time (days) for the unloaded dryer, collector and ambient. It was also observed that the dryer's (cabinet) temperature was higher than that of ambient. The daily average temperatures of ambient, cabinet and solar collector were 28.52, 45.23, and 45.38, respectively.

3.2 Testing on Load Results

The dryer was tested on load with pepper, fishes, okra, and yam. Typical result obtained for drying yam is presented in Fig 5.

Fig 5: Temperature against time for Yam.

Fig. 5 show a typical hourly temperature behaviour of the dryer. At an average ambient temperature of 28.0°C, the recorded solar collector temperature was 47.6°C while cabinet temperature of 41.6°C. This slightly lower temperature recorded in the cabinet could be attributed to the load utilising the heat generated for drying.

Fig. 6 shows the moisture removal rate for drying yam. The initial moisture content was 80%, while the final shelf moisture was 10%. However, the Double-sided dryer achieved a moisture content of 10.5% on the sixth day while the direct sun drying achieved 11% on the 10th day. This reduced the drying time by about 50%

Fig. 6: Rate of Moisture Removal per Day with Yam

3.3 Exegetic Efficiency.

The daily average exergetic efficiency for drying yam is shown in Fig. 7. From Fig. 7, the system has the highest average exergetic efficiency on day 2, and the lowest on day 1. The fluctuations in the efficiency could be attributed to variations in weather conditions. However, the dryer has overall average exergetic efficiency of 46.35% at a collector efficiency of 69.09%.

Fig 7: Average Daily Exegetic efficiency for Yam

3.4 Nutritional Evaluation

The proximate analysis result showed that the yam dried using the dryer has higher protein content of 5.96%, as against 3.34% obtained for the direct-sun dried product. The obtained protein content is closer to literature value of 7.4% [26–27].

4 CONCLUSION

A double sided inclined mixed-mode dryer was developed and evaluated on no-load and on-load with the samples of pepper (*Capsicum annum*) fish “panla” (Alaska Pollock) (*Gadus chalcogrammus*), white yam (*Dioscorea alata*), and okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*). The average temperature variation inside the drying chamber and collector during the drying process areranged from 35 to 60°C, at an average ambient temperature of 28°C, and an overall average exergetic efficiency of 46.35% at a collector efficiency of 69.09%. The solar dryer produced relatively better product in terms of nutrient composition compared to open sun drying, and exhibited sufficient ability to dry food items reasonably rapidly to a safe moisture level and simultaneously ensured a superior quality of the dried product. It is concluded that the passive solar dryer was more effective, reduced drying time in comparison with open sun drying and it helped in preserving the products for a longer shelf life.

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